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Deliverable D2:

Report describing suitable parameters for the definition of the accuracy of voltage and current instrument transformers in the frequency range up to 150 kHz including suitable calibration conditions and procedures for the accuracy evaluation

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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European Partnership

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Glossary

AC	Alternate Current
CT	Current Transformer
CVT	Capacitive VT
DC	Direct Current
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FSM	Frequency sweep method
IT	Instrument Transformers
LPCT	Low-Power CT
LPIT	Low-Power IT
NMI	National Metrology Institute
PI	Performance Index
PQ	Power Quality
RF	Radiofrequency
TFRD	Total Frequency Response Deviation
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
VT	Voltage Transformer

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Summary	4
2. Introduction	5
3. Relevant standards and related accuracy requirements	6
4. Accuracy test methods	11
4.1. Environmental conditions	12
4.2. Non-linearity and distortion	12
4.3. Frequency resolution, resolution bandwidth, observation time and aggregation	12
4.4. Performance requirements and uncertainty budget	13
5. Performance indexes (PIs)	18
5.1. Frequency domain	18
5.2. Time domain	19
6. Test waveforms	22
6.1. Frequency-domain test signals	22
6.2. Time-domain test signals	23
6.3. Set of test waveforms in WP2 and WP3	23
7. Conclusions	24
8. Bibliography	25

1. Summary

Standard requirements for Instrument Transformers of the IEC/EN 61869 family are initially discussed, considering then suitable performance indexes to benchmark and represent their performance, ranging from known amplitude and phase errors, to composite indexes based on a range of weighted frequency-domain expressions, as well as time-domain formulations including various types of norms, correlation functions, etc.

Correspondingly suitable test waveforms for frequency and time domain interpretation of tests are discussed, including a reference to the test protocol adopted for the round robin test within WP2 and WP3.

2. Introduction

The present deliverable D2 (pertaining to activities A1.3.9 and A1.3.10) organizes and summarizes the results of the activities A1.3.1 to A1.3.7 of Task 1.3 “Definition of accuracy, measurement methods and uncertainty limits”, with the intent of providing an organic and thorough overview to support the creation of the report at activity A1.3.11 and A1.3.12.

Considering the work carried out in Task 1.3 and the intention of supporting reporting to IEC/CENELEC TC 38, focus for what regards references is twofold, on scientific publications on the one hand and on standards and normative reports on the other hand.

The key elements covered by Task 1.3 are:

- definition of IT accuracy parameters at frequencies other than power frequency, and in particular at higher frequency in the supraharmmonic range;
- definition of measurement methods and test procedures for such parameters;
- definition of uncertainty limits and methods for evaluation of uncertainty.

Experimental tests were identified to be carried out by the partners in the form of round robin tests on selected sensors as part of WP3, defining a test procedure that synthesizes the results of these preliminary activities within Task 1.3. The activity is still ongoing due to delays in measurements and shipment of the samples.

3. Relevant standards and related accuracy requirements

This section contains an overview of the status of the published standards, having focused on IEC and CENELEC, as ANSI/IEEE contain very few information (IEEE Std. C57.13). The relevant identified standards are as follows.

- EN 61869-1 (2024) “Instrument Transformers – Part 1: General requirements”
- EN 61869-2 (2012) “Instrument Transformers – Part 2: Additional requirements for current transformers”
- EN 61869-3 (2012) “Instrument Transformers – Part 3: Additional requirements for inductive voltage transformers”
- IEC 61869-6 (2016) “Instrument Transformers – Part 6: Additional general requirements for low-power instrument transformers”
- IEC 61869-8 (2021) “Instrument Transformers – Part 8: Specific requirements for electronic Current Transformers” (draft)
- IEC 61869-10 (2018) “Instrument Transformers – Part 10: Additional requirements for low-power passive current transformers”
- IEC 61869-11 (2018) “Instrument Transformers – Part 11: Additional requirements for low-power passive voltage transformers”
- IEC 61869-14 (2019) “Instrument Transformers – Part 14: Additional requirements for current transformers for DC applications”
- IEC 61869-15 (2019) “Instrument Transformers – Part 15: Additional requirements for voltage transformers for DC applications”
- TR 61869-103 (2012) “Instrument Transformers – The use of instrument transformers for power quality measurement”

This group of standards is the most advanced and complete for what regards accuracy and metrological performance of IT. In the latest version requirements have also been extended to cover the supraharmmonic range, as shown in the following.

As clarified in the EN 61869-1, the bandwidth extension have been concretized in the definition of extended classes bearing the label “WB”, so wideband. The text is in italic to show that it is quoted: it is interesting to observe that the word “harmonic” is used also for spectral components up to 500 kHz.

Accuracy class extensions for harmonics (and supraharmonics) are:

- WB0 extension for harmonic frequencies up to the 13th harmonic;
- WB1 extension for harmonic frequencies up to 3 kHz;
- WB2 extension for harmonic frequencies up to 20 kHz;
- WB3 extension for harmonic frequencies up to 150 kHz;
- WB4 extension for wide bandwidth applications up to 500 kHz.

It is easy to see that the WB4 interval extends up to 500 kHz, so already in the so called RF (radiofrequency) interval, although phenomena have still behavior similar to supraharmonics.

Table 7 – WB0 extension for harmonics

Accuracy class	Ratio error at low frequency		Ratio error at harmonics based on f_r				Phase error at low frequency	Phase error at harmonics based on f_r			
	%		%				Degrees	Degrees			
	DC ^a	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th
0,1	+1 -100	+1 -30	±1	±2	±4	±8	±45	±1	±2	±4	±8
0,2 – 0,2 S ^b	+2 -100	+2 -30	±2	±4	±8	±16	±45	±2	±4	±8	±16
0,5 – 0,5 S ^b	+5 -100	+5 -30	±5	±10	±20	±20	±45	±5	±10	±20	±20
1 – 3 – 5	+10 -100	+10 -30	±10	±20	±20	±20	±45	±10	±20	±20	±20

^a DC coupling is allowed but not required.
^b The accuracy classes 0,2 S and 0,5 S apply only for current transformers.

Figure 1. Table 7 of EN 61869-1 (2024) with harmonic accuracy requirements of accuracy class WB0.

Table 8 – Accuracy class extensions for wide bandwidth applications

Accuracy class	Ratio error at frequencies shown below			Phase error at frequencies shown below		
	%			Degrees		
WB1	$f_r < f \leq 1$ kHz	$1 < f \leq 1,5$ kHz	$1,5 < f \leq 3$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 1$ kHz	$1 < f \leq 1,5$ kHz	$1,5 < f \leq 3$ kHz
WB2	$f_r < f \leq 5$ kHz	$5 < f \leq 10$ kHz	$10 < f \leq 20$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 5$ kHz	$5 < f \leq 10$ kHz	$10 < f \leq 20$ kHz
WB3	$f_r < f \leq 20$ kHz	$20 < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 20$ kHz	$20 < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz
WB4	$f_r < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$150 < f \leq 500$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$150 < f \leq 500$ kHz
0,1	±1	±2	±5	±1	±2	±5
0,2 – 0,2 S	±2	±4	±5	±2	±4	±5
0,5 – 0,5 S	±5	±10	±10	±5	±10	±20
1	±10	±20	±20	±10	±20	±20
Protection	±10	±20	±30	-	-	-

The accuracy classes 0,2 S and 0,5 S apply only for current transformers.

NOTE 1 Accuracy class extension WB4 is intended for very wide bandwidth applications like travelling-wave protections and fault locators where signal frequencies reach as high as 500 kHz. The use of relays based on travelling-wave analysis is a promising solution offering very accurate fault location. For instance, new devices based on such principles claim to be much more accurate than conventional reactance-based fault locators. This field is still evolving, but CTs and VTs suitable for these relays need a very large frequency range, hence the "extended" range up to 500 kHz. No consensus for general requirements for this kind of application is available at the date of the publication.

NOTE 2 Travelling wave relays are designed especially for this purpose and are very special (very large bandwidth, etc.). Although WB4 compliant ITs are very desirable, inductive CTs and CVTs often have not a sufficient bandwidth allowing relays and fault locators to accurately measure the traveling wave arrival times.

NOTE 3 Owing to the high bandwidth, the classes WB3 and WB4 are not compatible with digital signals in accordance with IEC 61869-9 and its standardized sampling rates.

Figure 2. Table 8 of EN 61869-1 (2024) with wide bandwidth accuracy requirements, derived from IEC 61000-4-7.

It's interesting to observe that these requirements are more restrictive than those reported in the EN 61869-6, Table 6A.2, for low-power ITs (the standard dating 2016, so 8 years earlier). With this update the EN 61869-1 becomes the reference for most of the test and accuracy requirements.

The EN 61869-6 is then discussed in the next page.

Table 6A.2 – Measuring accuracy classes

Accuracy class (at f_r)	Ratio error at low frequency		Ratio error (+/-) at harmonics					Phase displacement (+/-) at low frequency	Phase error (+/-) at harmonics			
								Degrees				
	0 Hz	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th	Above 13 th	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th
0,1	+1 % -100 %	+1 % -30 %	1 %	2 %	4 %	8 %	+8 % -100 %	45	1	2	4	8
0,2 0,2S	+2 % -100 %	+2 % -30 %	2 %	4 %	8 %	16 %	+16 % -100 %	45	2	4	8	16
0,5 0,5S	+5 % -100 %	+5 % -30 %	5 %	10 %	20 %	20 %	+20 % -100 %	45	5	10	20	20
1	+10 % -100 %	+10 % -30 %	10 %	20 %	20 %	20 %	+20 % -100 %	45	10	20	20	20
3 5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE 0 Hz in the first column means d.c. coupling is allowed but not required.

Figure 3. Table 6A.2 of EN 61869-6 (2016) with harmonic interval accuracy requirements (corresponding to table of Figure 1, taken from IEC 61869-1).

For LPITs the rated output burden is 2 MΩ/50 pF (so approximately the input impedance of a data acquisition system or oscilloscope, but allowing more capacitance than usually featured). It is written, however, that “for use on devices backward compatible with IEC 60044-8 or applications which require increased electromagnetic immunity, 2 kΩ/5000 pF and 20 kΩ/500 pF are acceptable. And MV applications, as well as in proximity to large power converters, may represent scenarios with noisy electromagnetic environment (benefiting from a lower-impedance termination, such as the 20 kΩ one).”

It is observed that such loading levels are suitable for harmonic measurements, as the cutoff frequency of the 2 kΩ/5000 pF is 15 kHz and the error due to capacitive shunting is 4.6% at 5 kHz and 0.8% at 2 kHz.

For what regards the identification of parameters to subject to test and test conditions, Table B.1 of TR 61869-103 (shown in Figure 4) provides a significant set of test cases covering the discussed frequency intervals in terms of amplitude and phase, but almost all lacking a description of the measurement method.

Table B.1 – Example of test table with possible main requirements for accuracy tests

Section and Parameter	Class	Measurement Method	Uncertainty	Measuring range	Influence Quantity range
Magnitude of voltage at fundamental frequency f50/60 Hz	PQ1	r.m.s. value of the voltage magnitude over a 10/12 cycles	± 0,1 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom
	PQ2	same	± 0,2 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom
	PQ3	same	± 0,5 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom
	PQ4	same	± 1,0 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom	5 %~150 % Unom
Phase-displacement of fundamental frequency 50/60 Hz	PQ1	To be defined	± 5 min	5 %~150 % Unom	
	PQ2	To be defined	±10 min	5 %~150 % Unom	
	PQ3	To be defined	± 25 min	5 %~150 % Unom	
	PQ4	To be defined	± 50 min	5 %~150 % Unom	
Magnitude of voltage with frequencies* 0Hz to 0,99fn ^a	PQ1	To be defined	± 5 % Um	1 %~10 % Unom	
	PQ2	To be defined	± 10 % Um	1 %~10 % Unom	
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Magnitude of harmonic voltage 2 nd to 50 th	PQ1	IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class I.	5 % Um Or IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class I	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1 to 5 % Unom	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 5 % Unom
	PQ2	IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class II	10 % Um Or 200 % IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class II	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1 to 5 % Unom	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 5 % Unom
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Phase displacement of harmonic voltage 2 nd to 50 th	PQ1	To be defined	± 5°	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1-5 % Unom	
	PQ2	To be defined	± 10°	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1 to 5 % Unom	
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Magnitude of interharmonic voltage 2 nd to 50 th	PQ1	IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class I.	5 % Um Or IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class I	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic subgroup 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic subgroup 1 to 5 % Unom	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic subgroup 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic subgroup 5 % Unom
	PQ2	IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class II	10 % Um Or 200 % IEC 61000-4-7:2002 Class II	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic subgroup 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic subgroup 1 to 5 % Unom	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic subgroup 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic subgroup 5 % Unom
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Phase displacement of interharmonic voltage 2 nd to 50 th	PQ1	To be defined	± 5°	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1 to 5 % Unom	
	PQ2	To be defined	± 10°	2 nd to 5 th Harmonic 1 to 10 % Unom 6 th to 50 th Harmonic 1 to 5 % Unom	
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Magnitude of harmonic voltage 50 th to 250 kHz ^a	PQ1	To be defined	±10 % Um	1 to 5 % Unom	5 % Unom
	PQ2	To be defined	±20 % Um	1 to 5 % Unom	5 % Unom
	PQ3	To be defined			
	PQ4	To be defined			
Phase displacement of harmonic voltage 50 th to 250 kHz ^a	PQ1	To be defined	?	1 to 5 % Unom	
	PQ2	To be defined	?	1 to 5 % Unom	
	PQ3	To be defined	?		
	PQ4	To be defined	?		
	PQ2	To be defined	To be defined		
	PQ3	To be defined	To be defined		
	PQ4	To be defined	To be defined		
	PQ4	To be defined	To be defined		

^a For special transducer types only.

Figure 4. Table B.1 of TR 61869-103 (2012) with PQ (power quality) IT classes and related requirements. To observe that at that time accuracy requirement for high-frequency intervals was only partially addressed.

Considering now the specific requirements in the product standards, the EN 61869-6 should be considered first; its sec. 7.2.6 lists the tests relevant to accuracy very synthetically, making reference to Annex 6D for circuits. In reality, other annexes of this standard clarify other two accuracy requirements.

- Measurement of output noise: with the primary disconnected, using a spectrum analyser the noise components should be measured.
- Distortion: distortion of the fundamental should be measured at least by supplying a “pure” sinusoid. The problem of the effectiveness of such pure single-tone test may be questioned if compared to a more affordable inter-modulation test, where, however, it is needed to find a relationship with the output of single-tone test. Distortion may occur in particular at large current intensity, due to non-linear effects, like saturation.

Another point raised by the IEC 61869-6 is the IT behavior in transient conditions: in its sec. 6B.5 for a matter of practical usefulness the discussion is focused on transients originating from fault conditions, examining traditional iron-core CTs (exposed to saturation) and LPITs (where the problem shifts to accurate reproduction of slow quasi-DC components, concluding that for their function associated to protection relays it is sensible that the measured AC component is unaltered and the behavior of the relay is substantially as desired). So this discussion is limited to current ITs.

In Annex 6C then the discussion is widened to include transients related to atmospheric discharges (lightning) and switching transients. In this case the discussion is focused only on voltage ITs.

In both cases the percent error is defined as the point by point difference between the provided waveform and the IT output normalized by the provided waveform.

Output noise is required to be specified in terms of spectral density; for ITs with nearly output white noise, a single number may be provided. It is advised to specific spectral density values in units at the primary side, so $V/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ and $A/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. No limits are provided (sec. 6.15 EN 61869-1).

4. Accuracy test methods

The EN 61869-1 at sec. 7.2.6.2 specifies tolerances for the burden at the secondary output. For other details of testing methods and setups it is written to refer to specific product standards. In reality some examples are provided in the Annex H of the EN 61869-1 standard.

Figure 5. Test circuit for accuracy measurements of (a) inductive CTs and (b) LPCTs (Annex H of EN 61869-1).

In general, the use of data acquisition systems and digital interfaces makes the test circuit more uniform and largely applicable.

Figure 6. Test circuit for digital accuracy measurements of LPCTs (Annex H of EN 61869-1).

Similar arrangements may be applied to voltage ITs, such as inductive VTs and CVTs.

The methods shown in TR 61869-103 (cited at sec. 7.2.15 of the EN 61869-1) and the EN 61869-1 itself are based on comparison with a reference IT, provided that the test signal is sufficiently stable for the duration of the measurement. (Note: The duration of each test for the round robin protocol is 1 second and it assumes, namely, substantial stability of the test signal and steady state conditions (including e.g. internal temperature) for the ITs under test and used as reference.)

In a wide perspective the degrees of freedom when testing accuracy of ITs may be summarized as follows:

1. Environmental conditions and IT conditioning, especially temperature excursion.
2. Presence of non-linearity in the IT under test that makes the test waveform and its components relevant: a small signal may be supplied under an AC or DC bias (that in AC varies with time, so that it requires disambiguation of the instantaneous value of the AC waveform defining the instantaneous bias point).
3. Evaluation of the non-linearity or rejection of non-linearity by-products, focusing on a single frequency measurement (providing a transfer function or frequency response); in case of evaluation of non-linearity by-products, time-domain (input-output mapping with extraction of deviations from linear relationships) or frequency-domain (spectrum and identification of harmonics of the test signal single frequency) methods may be used.
4. Influence of resolution bandwidth and frequency resolution, both in terms of spectral representation, that considering the amount of captured noise for each frequency bin and the rapidity to follow transient and intermittent signals. The latter is not relevant when using steady frequency-domain test signals, but must be considered for transients.
5. Definition of the test waveforms balancing exigencies of stability and reproducibility, test rapidity and suitability for linear and non-linear characteristics; they may be single sines, superposition of sines at different frequencies (e.g. fundamental and harmonics), transients e.g. of impulsive nature, etc.
6. Instrumentation that best implements the comparative function of the reference IT and the IT under test, depending on e.g. noise rejection (lock-in amplifiers may be used when analogue output signals are available), frequency interval (harmonics, supraharmonics, higher), detection of small distortion products (necessity of spectrum analysers or FFT analysers).
7. One last point regards the way the results of comparisons may be expressed, identifying the so called performance indexes.

The various points are discussed in the following, followed by a section dedicated to a reliable uncertainty budget for testing ITs in real conditions.

4.1. Environmental conditions

Not tested specifically the effect on the IT accuracy performance.

4.2. Non-linearity and distortion

It is observed that, although the distortion introduced by the IT due to its non-linearity is not explicitly accounted for, when using composite test waveforms made e.g. of a fundamental plus harmonics and supraharmonics, the final result will indicate if such "intrinsic" non-linearity exist and it is relevant from two standpoints:

- as reduced sensitivity at the frequencies of the injected components;
- as additional spectral components, resulting from either beating phenomena (intermodulation) of two components (the amplitude being the product of the single amplitudes) or harmonic by-products of the injected components alone.

An important point that was anticipated in Deliverable D1, at the end of sec. 8.2, is that results of IT testing at harmonic frequencies with and without fundamental can differ and there is no guarantee that the results are equivalent in all cases, although this method is accepted by IEC 61869-1. This is a point that is distinguished in the two single-tone (without fundamental) and multi-tone (with fundamental) suggested methods, discussed in the next section.

4.3. Frequency resolution, resolution bandwidth, observation time and aggregation

This is a long debated problem that have seen several proposed solutions, mostly dealt with in the IEC 61000-4-7, the IEC 61000-4-30 and CISPR standards.

The commonly used resolution bandwidths are established by the cited standards oriented to the evaluation of grid and equipment disturbance, rather than IT calibration. RBW values (corresponding to the frequency resolution, FR, for Fourier-oriented approaches) range from the 5 Hz associated to the 200 ms interval of the IEC 61000-4-7 to the 200 Hz shared among the CISPR 16-1-2 and the IEC 61000-4-30. Larger RBW (corresponding to larger impulse bandwidths) are beneficial to track fast transients and intermitted emissions with impulsive nature, and 1 kHz is sometimes selected, especially when spectrum analysers (rather than EMI receivers) are used [Sandrolini, 2022].

When measuring harmonics and mains fundamental related emissions, a common choice for FR is 50 Hz (and for RBW using Fourier methods, so to have complete coverage of the frequency interval).

When it comes to calibration of ITs, the choice of an integer number of fundamental periods is mandatory for synchronized measurements to avoid spectral leakage, much more effectively than using tapering windows, which might have an influence on the accuracy of the amplitude estimate [Sandrolini, 2021].

Aggregation and other forms of evaluation over longer time windows are suitable for compact and robust estimates of grid disturbance, but not for IT calibration, carried out in laboratory conditions with fairly stable and repeatable test signals.

It is nevertheless true that when measuring high-frequency phenomena in both the following cases too a narrow FR causes inconsistency of results.

- Phenomena with spectral components that are related to the fundamental at 50 Hz with a large harmonic number (2 kHz begins at the 40th harmonic number, 9 kHz at the 180th harmonic number and 150 kHz corresponds to the 3000th harmonic number) suffer from instability, due to the amplification of the 50 Hz fundamental instability; even a variation of 0.01 Hz becomes 1.8 Hz at 9 kHz and 30 Hz at 150 kHz, that is already in conflict with RBW values of 200 Hz; this may be fixed by using a controlled power supply with much better frequency stability.
- Switching and commutation phenomena are a source of high-frequency components unrelated from the mains fundamental, but following the stability of e.g. the PWM pattern generator or modulator clock and under too a narrow bandwidth inconsistency of the frequency bin number may occur, as well as significant reduction of the estimated amplitude when drifting towards the frequency bin boundaries. This, however, does not apply to IT calibration in laboratory controlled conditions, but rather to the measurement

Considering the influence of noise, it is true that larger RBW values let a higher noise power to affect the amplitude estimates of each frequency bin, but due to the higher aggregation of the noise spectrum components, the resulting noise power is more stable and less erratic, and easier to predict with noise statistics.

In light also of what is discussed in the next section in relation to the estimates in Table 1 and Table 2, small RBW allow keeping the noise contribution small, so that values between the known 5 and 200 Hz are advisable. For the highest supaharmonic frequencies using even a 200 Hz RBW may result in too many data points, for which a slight relaxation may be used if strictly necessary.

In case of use of repetitive signals, longer observation times and averaging may be used.

4.4. Performance requirements and uncertainty budget

The wideband extensions WB0 through WB4 reviewed in sec. 3 are a convenient and compact way to characterize the IT high-frequency behavior in addition to the simple indication of the base accuracy class. For LPITs and SAMUs at least the WB0 extension is mandatory, whereas for conventional instrument transformers all extensions are optional.

In regard to the calibration of ITs, NMIs provide calibration and traceability to the SI system of a so called “transfer standard”, that may be a current or voltage comparator, a current or voltage sensor, a reference transformer, or any another high-accuracy device that is part of the accuracy quantification setup. This transfer standard is used by other laboratories or by IT manufacturers to verify the accuracy of their ITs.

Traceability and validity of such assessment is ensured by the calibration chain, starting from the uncertainty that characterizes the uncertainty documented by the NMIs, u_{NMI} . This is the lowest value possible of uncertainty, including all influencing factors (environmental conditions, external interference, connections, reference instrumentation and samples, non-linear effects and non-idealities, operators' influence, etc.) under control conditions.

These influencing factors are “replicated” at the receiving laboratory (e.g. IT manufacturer), but overall uncertainty is deemed to increase due to less controlled conditions, less performing instrumentation, etc. In

general, an good estimate for a laboratory with suitable procedures, competence and instrumentation tells that uncertainty increases by a factor of 3 to 5, so that $u_{LAB} = K_{LAB} \times u_{NMI} = 3\div 5 \times u_{NMI}$. The target accuracy (or, uncertainty) of the IT, u_{IT} , as device should be larger with a margin than the uncertainty that the laboratory applies to its calibrations, for which the Test Uncertainty Ratio (TUR) is defined:

$$TUR = \frac{u_{IT}}{u_{LAB}} \quad (1)$$

required usually to be ≥ 3 , so that there is an order of magnitude or slightly more between the provided high-accuracy transfer standard and the IT under test for their uncertainties. In other words the calibration of high-accuracy and low uncertainty ITs requires high-performance transfer standards, instrumentation and procedures.

To fix ideas, an IT with a declared accuracy of 0.1% necessitates to be calibrated with a transfer standard of at least 0.01% uncertainty, if not better. It is observed that this is in general true for the fundamental where the accuracy requirement is most stringent, whereas it is relaxed for increasing frequency. Class 0.1 (which is stated at the fundamental), for example, sees requirements of $\pm 1\%$, $\pm 2\%$ and $\pm 5\%$ for increasing frequency, as shown in Figure 2. Transfer standard and procedures, then, receive a similar relaxation, necessitating only a 0.05-0.2% performance, with some margin.

An aspect to consider is that the internal and output signals provided by the IT reduce in amplitude when operating at high frequency, simply because the components to measure are (much) smaller than the fundamental and decreasing. This brings into play two additional aspects:

- it is important the transfer standard and instrumentation are all calibrated for such small signals;
- small signals in the mV range are more exposed to noise, to limited resolution and sensitivity of instrumentation (e.g. comparator or data acquisition board) and non-linearity by-products (larger or similar components may pollute at harmonics of their frequency, for which it is important that frequencies of test signal supraharmmonic components are prime with non-overlapping harmonic terms, at least for the lowest harmonic numbers).

From this the importance of comparing the results of single-tone and multi-tone tests (see below), to spot out any effect of non-linearity and distortion.

Two main frequency-domain methods can be used to assess the performance of ITs at high frequencies, such as in the supraharmmonic range:

- Frequency sweep method (FSM): a sinusoidal signal is injected with variable frequency, selected one by one, during the sweep, measuring the output voltage or current of the IT; no fundamental signal is applied.
- Multi-tone method (MTM): a sinusoidal signal at the fundamental frequency is applied with superimposed one or several harmonic (or supraharmmonic) components, measuring the output voltage or current of the IT; the fundamental may be then attenuated by filtering (high-pass or notch filter) to increase the dynamic range of the acquisition system downstream

Both methods see an increase of measurement uncertainty as the frequency increases and the uncertainty budget may become the limiting factor when determining whether an IT meets a given accuracy class at a specific frequency.

Starting from an assumed u_{NMI} value for the reference standard, to which the uncertainty of the measurement setup, instrumentation and method should be added, we can derive the minimum accuracy requirement that may be applied to the IT and verified. As stated above, the assumed scaling coefficient for the uncertainty budget is 3÷5 (assumed 3 in general, having already accounted for quantization noise and shunt uncertainty explicitly and not included in this figure; 5 may be taken only for very low values of uncertainty where other influencing elements becomes relevant and get in) to pass to u_{LAB} and a minimum $TUR = 3$, then, for the IT accuracy:

$$u_{IT} = TUR \times u_{LAB} = TUR \times K_{LAB} \times u_{NMI} = 9 \times u_{NMI}$$

The two tables provided in Deliverable D1 (former Table 4 and 5) have been verified against some scientific publications, providing independent estimates of the uncertainty values initially written, with the objective of validating the approach and deriving documented uncertainty intervals. The two new tables report the previous estimates in black and the new estimates in blue; in the text then there are justifications for margins and assumption, together with a clarification of the calculations.

It is observed that the higher u_{NMI} values in the MTM case do not reflect a degradation of the NMI calibration itself, but rather the increased uncertainty of the reference measurement system when operated under multi-tone conditions. Since measurement uncertainty depends on both the reference standard and the test

method, the simultaneous presence of multiple frequency components introduces additional uncertainty contributions, which are reflected in the higher assumed u_{NMI} values in Table 2.

Another small change to the previous tables consist in introducing 50 kHz to split the supraharmonic frequency range, resulting in 10 kHz – 50 kHz and 50 kHz – 150 kHz with the following benefits: 50 kHz is more “central” with a ratio of 5 on the left and of 3 on the right, that aligns with the WB definitions of the EN 61869-1 (Figure 2) and also with the experimental results of the state-of-the-art VSL system [Rom, 2025] showing an increase of reported uncertainty right about at 30/50 kHz.

Table 1: Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the frequency sweep method (FSM)

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical u_{NMI}	Minimum IT Accuracy
> 10 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.014%	0.21%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.024%	0.36%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.04%	0.60%
> 1 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.10%	0.90%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.10%	0.90%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.11%	1.0%
> 10 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.04%	0.60%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.08%	0.72%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.20%	1.8%
> 1 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.11%	1.65%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.13%	1.95%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.22%	3.3%

Table 2: Recommended minimum accuracy for harmonics using the multi-tone method (MTM)

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical u_{NMI}	Minimum IT Accuracy
> 10 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.04%	0.45%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.07%	0.54%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.12%	0.80%
> 1 mV	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.22%	1.98%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.22%	1.98%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.24%	2.16%
> 10 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.12%	1.08%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.20%	1.8%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.40%	3.6%
> 1 mA	1 kHz – 10 kHz	0.26%	2.34%
	10 kHz – 50 kHz	0.33%	2.97%
	50 kHz – 150 kHz	0.44%	3.96%

Notes:

(1) State-of-the-art PTB measurement system [Mohns, 2018] operates at low frequency (up to a few kHz) in single tone and has a basic uncertainty of 0.003% at $k=2$.

(2) State-of-the-art VSL measurement system [Rom, 2025] operates over a wide range of frequencies (between 50 Hz and 150 kHz) in single tone and has a basic uncertainty of 0.001% up to 10 kHz and 0.012% at 150 kHz both at $k=2$.

Repeatability shown in Fig. 7 of the paper is 0.0005% up to 10 kHz and then about 0.003-0.005% at 150 kHz.

The authors underline that “these uncertainties do not include the uncertainty of the reference CT” and for this the reported figures should be rounded up, but expecting anyway that the reference CT has an uncertainty lower than that reported for the system and considering that the observed large repeatability,

once included, would absorb the CT contribution.

As a confirmation of the considerations that follow at point (4), it is observed that the used signals in this publication aren't close to the values shown in the two tables, but rather the secondary current signal is in the order of 100-200 mA with quantization noise below 1 μ A, resulting in less than 0.001% uncertainty.

(3) It is remarked that uncertainty figures are worse for secondary current output due to the contribution of the reading shunt both in terms of its uncertainty (a fair figure should be assumed) and noise contribution (that depends if the measurement is narrowband, such as FSM, or broadband, such as MTM). The uncertainty due to parasitics is frequency dependent and may range from e.g. tens of ppm to hundreds with increasing frequency (the formula provided for the WT5000 is $0.03\% + f/500\text{kHz} \%$, providing 0.075% at 10-50 kHz and 0.2% at 50-150 kHz). A 0.1 Ω resistor has 40 pV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ thermal noise (Johnson noise) which contributes only 4 ppm with MTM full band and 0 for the FSM, so it is negligible. A 1 Ω shunt causes a 3.2 times larger noise influence, still barely visible, amounting to 13 ppm (0.0013) for MTM only. A value of 1 Ω is assumed not to worsen too much the current reading; of course the WT5000 cannot be used in this case.

(4) Regarding the different output levels, the difference between "10" and "1" for the same quantity (mV or mA) considers the relevance of noise and the reduction by a factor of 10 of the signal-to-noise ratio passing from 10 to 1. The mA part then has larger uncertainty for introducing a further conversion (the shunt). The problem of small signals becomes evident when even a high-performance instrument like Yokogawa WT5000 (used in [Rom, 2025]) with its $\pm(0.01\%$ of reading + 0.02% of range) "surrenders" to a range term of 30% relative to the 1 mV fed to its minimum range of 1.5 V. A 16-bit acquisition system with better smaller ranges (such as Picoscope 5442D) reduces this uncertainty term to 7%, whereas a low-uncertainty acquisition system (like National Instrument 9205, always 16 bit) further goes down to 1%. Moving to 24-bit systems (such as NI9238) the improvement is only to about 0.3-0.4%, always larger than the other uncertainty terms; a high-end 24-bit system (such as PXI-4462) is barely able to achieve 0.1%. So, probably the assumed system was a 24-bit acquisition board, like NI9238, which, however, has a maximum sampling rate of 50 kSa/s, so not able to go beyond about 10 kHz bandwidth, and also the PXI-4462 is limited to 200 kSa/s, so not covering the entire supraharmmonic interval either.

It seems then that only instruments like the Agilent/Keysight 3458A sampling voltmeter can approach the required behavior with low-level signals, with an AC accuracy at 10 mV and 100 mV ranges of 0.09% of reading + 0.06% of range (that translates into 0.15% at both 10 mV and 1 mV, provided that the used range is 100 mV and 10 mV, and this is 2x better than a high-performance 24 bit data acquisition system).

A lock-in amplifier approach is usable only for single-tone measurements and represent an elaborated technique compared to the more straightforward data acquisition. Reported uncertainties are in the order of 0.01% for measured levels even below 1 mV down to 10 μ V [Cultrera, 2025].

This analysis clarifies that the data acquisition part is the one limiting the uncertainty budget and that a custom solution, including selectable amplification and filtering is necessary.

It is anticipated that the key factors to keep the values under control with respect to what previously reported in Deliverable D1 are the choice of a large values shunt (1 Ω) that is valid only for weak secondary current signals, and the low noise of the acquisition system, assumed 1 μ V. A ten times smaller shunt immediately increases by the same amount the values related to current at the secondary output. A ten times larger noise immediately increases by the same amount the values related to the low levels, namely 1 mV and 1 mA. The two worsening scenarios combined make impossible measurements in the 1 mA case.

The results presented in the two tables may be overall represented by an equation that shows approximately the exposed values:

$$u_{LAB}(\text{ampl, method, X}) = K_{\text{method}} \sqrt{u_{0,X}^2 \times (1 + \sqrt[3]{\text{freq}}) + \left(\frac{u_{n,X}}{\text{ampl}}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where:

- ampl secondary signal amplitude, i.e. 10 mV, 1 mV, 10 mA, 1 mA;
- freq frequency measured in multiples of 10 kHz and taking the value for 1-10 kHz as 1;
- X voltage or current output;
- $u_{0,X}$ basic uncertainty for quantity X (larger for current, and in that case includes shunt); the formula for the shunt is $u_{sh} = 0.03\% + \text{freq}/(500 \text{ kHz}) \%$ (using the expression of the manufacturer of the WT5000, Yokogawa), so that $u_{0,I} = \sqrt{u_{0,V}^2 + u_{sh}^2}$

- $u_{n,x}$ equivalent uncertainty for noise and resolution of data acquisition, that does not depend on frequency;
- $u_{f,x}$ equivalent uncertainty for frequency;
- K_{method} if FSM, =1 ; if MTM an appropriate scaling must be considered; in fact not all uncertainty terms should be multiplied, like those due to noise, but only those related to the analysis of the signal (and a synced DFT with narrow bandwidth may be used) and some non-linear effects, so probably a 2÷3 value is more indicate, considering that noise and shunt contributions make more than 50% of the uncertainty budget.

To demonstrate the values appearing in the tables, we can set the quantities as follows for the 10 mV case:

- $u_{0,v} = 0.01\%$ for the first row of Table 1, so considering the 1 kHz – 10 kHz interval for voltage;
- considering a noise contribution of the data acquisition system in the order of $u_{n,v} = 1 \mu\text{V}$, this adds 0.1% with $\text{ampl} = 1 \text{ mV}$ and 0.01% with $\text{ampl} = 10 \text{ mV}$;
- considering the frequency bands the worsening vs frequency corresponds to 1 for the 1 – 10 kHz band, approximately 1.8 for the 10 – 50 kHz band and 3.0 for the 50 – 150 kHz band, having taken the geometric mean of the two extremes of each band measured in “10 kHz” units;
- so,

The tables show that with extremely quiet and accurate data acquisition, IT accuracy can be verified for the largest of the two small measured levels (10 mV and 10 mA), always considering that data acquisition noise and resolution play an important role in the overall uncertainty budget. Lower secondary levels represent a serious obstacle to a reliable verification of IT, for the accuracy classes of the IEC61869-1.

In particular, due to the broadband nature of the MTM (multi-tone) and the presence of the fundamental, the uncertainty budget may be assumed from 3 to 5 times higher. This clearly indicates the problem that sophisticated techniques, like the use of lock-in amplifiers, may have limited applicability to single-tone sweeps. To remember, MTM allows verifying IT non-linearity and distortion, including its operation in realistic conditions of superposition of many harmonic/suprharmonic components and a fundamental.

5. Performance indexes (PIs)

Performance indexes synthesize and implement the assessment of IT accuracy and may be scalar or vectorial, frequency- or time-domain based, etc. They are reviewed and discussed in the following.

5.1. Frequency domain

Performance indexes (PIs) range from the classical amplitude error and phase error, to more elaborated combinations of error components extending them to the harmonic and supraharmonic interval.

Single frequency ratio error $\varepsilon(f)$ and phase error $\Delta\varphi(f)$:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r X_s(f) - X_p(f)}{X_p(f)} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\varphi(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (2)$$

where k_r is the expected IT ratio, X indicates either voltage or current for generality and subscripts “p” and “s” indicate primary or secondary, respectively.

The ratio $\varepsilon(f)$, if calculated not using magnitudes, but complex quantities, may become the so called “harmonic transfer function” $H_{IT}(f)$ (the frequency-dependent complex ratio of the IT), also named “Frequency-Response Deviation Index”.

A straightforward extension is the combined evaluation over an assigned frequency interval or band, calculating indexes like:

- the maximum of $H_{IT}(f)$ expressed also as the ratio -1: $\max|H_{IT}(f)| = \max \left| \frac{k_r X_s}{X_p} - 1 \right|$ (3)
- some total rms or weighted rms combination of the frequency values as shown below.

In fact, extending the single-frequency indexes to weighted quantities covering an assigned frequency interval, we get a PI called Total Frequency Response Deviation ε_{TFRD} [Crotti, 2022]:

$$\varepsilon_{TFRD} = \frac{k_r TFRD_s - TFRD_p}{TFRD_p} \quad (4)$$

where

$$TFRD_p = \frac{\sum_{f=f_1}^{f_N} X_p^2(f)}{X_p(f^*)} \quad TFRD_s = \frac{\sum_{f=f_1}^{f_N} X_s^2(f)}{X_s(f^*)} \quad (5)$$

and f^* indicates the reference frequency, that may be the center band of the interval, the largest component, etc.

A similar approach is taking the quantity $H_{IT}(f)$ as expressed above (with notation separating the ratio and the “-1”) and consider it a complex quantity named ξ to split then in a deterministic and statistic part:

$$\xi = \xi_d - \xi_s \quad (6)$$

where the statistic part represents the unknown distortion of the IT itself [Faifer, 2024]. As a remark, this part is unknown, but in principle deterministic, as the mechanism at its origin is the IT non-linearity.

Another PI borrowed from synchrophasor metrology (IEEE C37.118) is the Total Vector Error (TVE), which was classified as a dynamic index in [Crotti, 2022], but limited to the fundamental. Extension to the entire frequency range with a quantity that depends on frequency is straightforward and was proposed in various contexts, i.e. such as vs harmonic order, vs frequency, etc. [Faifer, 2017][Narduzzi, 2018]. It is another manipulation of the $H_{IT}(f)$ quantity, this time not expressing separately the complex quantities, but providing their amplitude: so, it is a scalar that weights both ratio and phase errors.

$$TVE = \sqrt{\frac{[\operatorname{Re}\{k_r X_s(f)\} - \operatorname{Re}\{X_p(f)\}]^2 + [\operatorname{Im}\{k_r X_s(f)\} - \operatorname{Im}\{X_p(f)\}]^2}{[\operatorname{Re}\{X_p(f)\}]^2 + [\operatorname{Im}\{X_p(f)\}]^2}} \quad (7)$$

In this representation the vectors of secondary and primary measured quantities are assumed to be very generally frequency vectors, without any further restriction on harmonic components or similar. As harmonic components they appeared in [Crotti, 2022].

Another approach that has the merit of being well known and tested is using existing PQ indexes to benchmark ITs accuracy: a weighted sum of harmonic components is, for example, an all-comprehensive index for that frequency range, that summarizes the amplitude of harmonic components and may be used as well to summarize the IT behavior vs frequency at the harmonic frequencies, when fed with composite test signals [Betti, 2025].

The proposed indexes are all variants of THD tailored to a specific frequency interval (named “harmonic” [100 Hz – 2500 Hz], “extended” [2550 – 9000 Hz] and “supraharmonic” [9050 – 150000 Hz]), assuming, first, an analysis carried out at multiples of 50 Hz, but, then, testing also other smaller frequency resolutions (e.g. 5 Hz).

$$THD = \frac{\sum_{h=2}^{h_{\max}} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (8)$$

where the summation of harmonic components is extended up to h_{\max} , usually taken as 40 or 50.

$$TWD = \frac{\sqrt{X^2 - X_1^2}}{X_1} \quad (9)$$

where X^2 denotes the total rms squared of quantity X .

The THD index is then applied to the three frequency intervals identified above, deriving

$$THD_{PQ} = \frac{\sum_{h=2}^{50} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (10)$$

$$THD_{EX} = \frac{\sum_{h=51}^{180} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (11)$$

$$THD_{SH} = \frac{\sum_{h=181}^{450} X_h^2}{X_1} \quad (12)$$

and, correspondingly, three versions of such metrics normalized by TWD may also be derived:

$$\rho_{PQ} = \frac{THD_{PQ}}{TWD} \quad (13)$$

$$\rho_{EX} = \frac{THD_{EX}}{TWD} \quad (14)$$

$$\rho_{SH} = \frac{THD_{SH}}{TWD} \quad (15)$$

These indexes may be used to test IT performance, starting from a reference test signal, for which all these indexes can be calculated providing a reference result. The signal is then fed to the IT under test and the output is treated as a new signal, to which the indexes are again applied. The two sets of indexes provide a quick way to evaluate the IT response. Due to the nature of the proposed indexes, only the amplitude response may be evaluated, as all such indexes are invariant to phase.

5.2. Time domain

The ratio error may be transferred into time domain with direct application to recorded waveforms $X_s(t)$ and $X_p(t)$, where they represent e.g. a pulse, surge or similar transient. Being not an exact one-to-one translation

from frequency to time domain, its name has been changed to E_{L2} , being an L2 norm of the time-domain error:

$$E_{L2} = \frac{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} [k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)]^2 dt}}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} [x_p(t)]^2 dt}} \quad (16)$$

and the discrete time implementation is straightforward.

A remark is due for the verification of performance at high frequency: the two signals $x_s(t)$ and $x_p(t)$ are assumed in phase with the same origin, but $x_s(t)$ is unavoidably delayed by the IT delay. This may seem natural as also in frequency domain the phase rotation caused by the IT is well captured in the phase error quantity. However, here in time domain a delay would translate in an amplitude error: let's think for example in a perfect reproduction at the secondary of the primary signal, except for the introduced delay; in signal theory this is a linear phase system that introduces only a constant delay for all signal components, but the difference at the numerator of (16) would result in a significant amplitude error. For this reason, $x_s(t)$ and $x_p(t)$ should be aligned by the amount of delay estimated for the IT before proceeding with the calculation of various forms of error (e.g. by difference).

Taking the maximum instead of the L2 norm (which, for clarity, is equivalent to rms), then

$$E_{\max} = \max \left| \frac{k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)}{x_p(t)} \right| \quad (17)$$

that may be useful for absolute accuracy, spotting out worst-case instantaneous deviations, and possibly finds application when ITs are used connected to protection relays. A smoothed version may be adopted, where occasionally excessive noise and spikes are leveled (pruned) before feeding the signals to E_{\max} .

Another similar metric is obtained taking not the maximum, but the cumulated absolute error, so what is called "integral absolute error":

$$E_{IAE} = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \left| \frac{k_r x_s(t) - x_p(t)}{x_p(t)} \right| dt \quad (18)$$

All these metrics may be recalculated in their corresponding weighted versions, so multiplying the error by a weighting function $w(t)$ that filters to emphasize certain time intervals, such as the importance of the peak amplitude of an impulse, rather than matching its tail.

It is quite interesting to shift the paradigm from quantification of error to quantification of similarity, thus adopting a series of approaches that may be based on:

- correlation coefficient (or cosine similarity)

$$r = \frac{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t)) x_p(t) dt}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t))^2 dt} \sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (x_p(t))^2 dt}} \quad (19)$$

- correlation function (that is a more general expression, where the correlation coefficient r corresponds to its value at 0 lag)

$$R(\tau) = \frac{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t)) x_p(t + \tau) dt}{\sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (k_r x_s(t))^2 dt} \sqrt{\int_{T_1}^{T_2} (x_p(t))^2 dt}} \quad (20)$$

where the integrals under square root at the denominator represent the normalization by the rms values of the primary and secondary (scaled) signals, as it was done above for the correlation coefficient.

Also for the calculation of the correlation coefficient r and correlation function $R(\tau)$ the delay introduced by the IT is relevant:

- in the case of r $x_s(t)$ must be adjusted for the delay to make the scalar product with $x_p(t)$ meaningful;
- for $R(\tau)$ in reality the delay comes out from the calculation as the τ value corresponding to the maximum of $R(\tau)$; this is in fact one of the most straightforward ways to determine the delay of a system; the interpretation of $R(\tau)$, then, must be done taking τ on the abscissa as the reference.

6. Test waveforms

Addressing the discussed performance indexes, test waveforms in both standards and scientific literature have been conceived as superposition of:

- DC or AC fundamental “bias”;
- harmonics of different amplitude;
- supraharmonics of different amplitude.

6.1. Frequency-domain test signals

The most commonly used and preferred frequency-domain test signal is substantially a superposition of the three components: bias, harmonics and supraharmonics. An additional term may be an inter-harmonic component that, however, causes variability between the fundamental cycles, not being an integer multiple of the fundamental. The same may be said in general for supraharmonics, but their frequency is much higher and the cycle-to-cycle variability is lesser, notwithstanding that they may be easily generated synchronized with the fundamental (without loss of generality).

Going into the details of the most suitable amplitudes and frequency ranges and considering the typical sources of disturbance and disturbing/distorting components at LV and MV, it is possible to say Supraharmonic sources (photovoltaic parks, wind farms, electric vehicle charging stations) are a source of emissions mostly located in the first 50 kHz with amplitudes in voltage generally below a few V, as dictated by the EMC compatibility levels for residential, industrial and public networks (IEC 61000-2-2 and IEC 61000-2-4).

Typical switching frequencies are in the range of 4 to 20 kHz (typically 8 kHz, 10 kHz and 16 kHz are the mostly used) and harmonics of such switching components can be significant up to order 3 to 5, namely the previously announced 50 kHz, although resonances and specific scenarios do not exclude relevant components also in the rest of the supraharmonic range.

In terms of current values up to 1 A have been observed and in general some hundreds of mA for nominal currents in the order of tenths of A up to a hundred, so in the order of some %, 5% at most.

It may be concluded that tests of ITs should be carried out at distortion levels of some % of the fundamental to cover typical representative operating conditions. Supraharmonic amplitudes of 5% are already rare, although in extreme cases where the IT function would be early warning to protect network assets, even loosely quantified accuracy is acceptable (due to the relevance of the early warning function) [Mariscotti, 2024].

We may thus synthesize the appropriate test levels as follows, remembering that IT accuracy verification does not imply the test of the entire operating range, rather the selection of relevant operating points in the expected span of supraharmonic distortion values.

- Voltage test levels: from 0.5% to 2% of nominal rms amplitude for LV applications for each high-frequency component, with possible derating (if necessary) above 50 kHz depending on frequency. For MV levels, a practical adaptation (also supported by grid measurement results) amplitude may be reduced privileging the low-frequency portion where larger components are expected: up to 1% of nominal rms amplitude up to 10 kHz, 0.2–0.5% between 10 and 50 kHz and 0.1% for the 50–150 kHz interval. This aligns with literature and experimental findings on the one hand and is achievable with available instrumentation.
- Current test levels: similar to the voltage test levels in p.u. of the nominal rms current.

Superposition of more than one supraharmonic component may be used to test phenomena of non-linearity and resulting inter-modulation products.

In both cases when testing with superposition of more than one supraharmonic component, the overall peak value of the supraharmonic test signal is the sum of the peak amplitudes, as it cannot be excluded that instantaneously over the entire test time interval all supraharmonic components are in phase. In this case, to cope with the capabilities of the instrumentation (in particular amplifiers), individual test levels of each supraharmonic component should be correspondingly reduced.

6.2. Time-domain test signals

The use of impulsive test waveforms has not been discussed extensively in the literature, except for the proposal of using a tapered sinc pulse with the objective of testing a multitude of frequency points with one test waveform (thanks to the flat spectrum) [Betti, 2023].

The sinc has an ideally rectangular spectrum where all components are zero after the cutoff frequency f_c . To this aim the sinc must have the form

$$s(t) = \frac{\sin(\pi t/T_c)}{\pi t/T_c} \quad (21)$$

where $T_c = 1/f_c$. Due to truncation of the sinc() signal in any practical implementation, the spectrum is corrupted and deviates from the desired rectangular form due to spectral leakage. As commonplace, in such case the time-domain signal may be shaped by a tapering window that controls spectral leakage; a tapering window with fast frequency decay should be selected in order to have as most rectangular as possible spectral shape.

In addition, aiming at generating large test amplitudes with already available instruments, surge and fast transient waveforms may be considered, as commonly used for electromagnetic immunity tests (IEC 61000-4-5 and IEC 61000-4-4 standards for definition and application of surges and fast transients, respectively).

In this case the IT transfer function is estimated by using a standard non-parametric estimate based on auto- and cross-spectra (indicated by $S_{pp}()$ and $S_{sp}()$, respectively):

$$\hat{H}_{IT}(f) = \frac{S_{sp}(f)}{S_{pp}(f)} \quad (22)$$

The calculation of $S_{sp}()$ is done with the cross-spectrum between $X_s(t)$ and $X_p(t)$. Improvements may be introduced by simply averaging between different tests: it is noted in fact that, despite some variability between tests due to some parametric changes (e.g. self heating of a component), $x_s(t)$ will follow anyway the new $x_p(t)$, providing consistent values of $H_{IT}()$, although the same cannot be said for the single terms S_{sp} and S_{pp} . The so determined $H_{IT}()$ then provides information on amplitude and phase and will be compared to the nominal k_r .

It is observed that the so-determined $H_{IT}()$ is a transfer function determined under an impulsive excitation, so that, depending on the amplitude excursion, linearity assumptions are stressed and may become invalid.

6.3. Set of test waveforms in WP2 and WP3

The set of waveforms discussed for the round robin test on the three CTs and three VTs is well representative of the approach above in sec. 6.1.

In a frequency domain perspective, the test waveforms set is composed of:

- F0: sine wave at 50 Hz with amplitude at 10 %, 20 %, 50 %, 80 %, 100 %, 120 % of the rated input;
- FH1: sine wave at 50 Hz 100 % amplitude + SH sine tone at frequencies 9, 10, 15, 20, 35, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150 kHz, zero phase, with amplitude equal to 2 % of the rated input at the fundamental;
- FH1N: variation of FH1 with different choices of frequencies and amplitude, and varying the phase relationship;
- FH1A: simple variation of FH1 where the SH amplitude is varied from the fixed 2 % from 1 % up to 10 % (if attainable, depending on the capability of the signal source);
- A simplified version of FH1, where all SH components are applied simultaneously; to avoid issues due to the limited capability of the signal source (the instantaneous SH amplitude value would be 10 %), the amplitude is reduced to 1 % for each component.

A sinc to be provided by UNIBO was included as an optional test (time domain transient signal as in sec. 6.2).

7. Conclusions

Deliverable D2, after the introduction of the present requirements for IT accuracy, has shown indexes in frequency and time domain, suitable to characterize the IT behaviour under test, and test waveforms to suitably test ITs in frequency and time domain.

The discussed frequency-domain indexes range from the classical amplitude and phase error and TVE to synthetic indexes weighting the error vs frequency, including variants of known power quality indexes.

The time-domain indexes include various norms of the error equation, translating the concept of amplitude and phase error into a point-by-point instantaneous error. This error vector is then evaluated by the Euclidean norm, the max or its integral (cumulative error) in order to derive a single value. To make such time-domain indexes frequency selective, suitable weighting may be introduced multiplying by a filter function.

The discussed test waveforms are divided in “frequency domain oriented” test, with the composition of a fundamental with harmonic and supraharmonic components of various amplitude (as presently used for calibration), and “time domain oriented” tests where two possible approaches are discussed (the use of a truncated sinc with a corresponding boxcar spectrum profile and of a pulsed waveform, closer e.g. to surges and fast transients, exploiting then impulse response and power spectrum identification).

8. Bibliography

- [1] G. Crotti et al., "How Instrument Transformers Influence Power Quality Measurements: A Proposal of Accuracy Verification Tests," *Sensors*, 2022, 22, 5847. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22155847>
- [2] C. Betti et al., "Experimental Validation of Simple Power Quality Indices for Frequency Content Assessment up to 150 kHz," *Sensors*, 2025, 25, 6716. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25216716>
- [3] C. Betti et al., "Design of a Windowed Sinc for a Simplified Characterization of Low-Power Current Transformers", 2023 IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (I2MTC). <https://doi.org/10.1109/I2MTC53148.2023.10175911>
- [4] G. Crotti et al., "Evaluation of Voltage Transformers' Accuracy in Harmonic and Interharmonic Measurement," *Open Journal of Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2022, 1, 9000310. <https://doi.org/10.1109/OJIM.2022.3198473>
- [5] M. Faifer et al., "A New Method to Represent the Harmonic Measurement Accuracy of Current Transformers," *IEEE Trans. on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2024, 73, 9001611. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2024.3353857>
- [6] M. Faifer et al., "Nonlinear Behavioral Modeling of Voltage Transformers in the Frequency Domain: Comparing Different Approaches," *IEEE Trans. on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2020, 69, 8137-8145. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2020.2987740>
- [7] C. Narduzzi et al., "Fast-TFM—Multifrequency Phasor Measurement for Distribution Networks," *IEEE Trans. on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2018, 67, 1825-1835. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2018.2809080>
- [8] A Mariscotti and A Mingotti, "The Effect of Supraharmonic Distortion in MV and LV AC Grids," *Sensors*, 2024, vol. 24, 8, id 2465. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24082465>
- [9] L. Sandrolini and A. Mariscotti, "Impact of Short-Time Fourier Transform Parameters on the Accuracy of EMI Spectra Estimates in the 2-150 kHz Supraharmonic Interval," *Electrical Power System Research*, June 2021, Vol. 195, 107130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2021.107130>
- [10] L. Sandrolini, A. Mariscotti, "Waveform and Spectral Characteristics of Supraharmonic Unsymmetrical Conducted EMI of Switched-Mode Power Supplies," *Electronics*, Vol. 11, no. 4, 591, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11040591>
- [11] E. Mohns and P. Räther, "Test equipment and its effect on the calibration of instrument transformers," *J. Sensors and Sensing Systems*, Vol. 7, pp 339–347, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.5194/jsss-7-339-2018>
- [12] M. Rom, H. E. van den Brom, E. Houtzager, R. van Leeuwen, D. van der Born, G. Rietveld and F. Muñoz, "Measurement System for Current Transformer Calibration from 50 Hz to 150 kHz Using a Wideband Power Analyzer," *Sensors*, Vol. 25, pp. 5429, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25175429>
- [13] A. Cultrera, J. Medved, P. Durandetto, M. Ortolano, A. Sosso and L. Callegaro, "Magnitude and Phase Calibration of Lock-In Amplifiers, and Analysis of the Noise Response," *IEEE Trans. on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2025, pp. 1-15, 1825-1835. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tim.2025.3553954>